

1 Nuclear factor discovery in the placenta.

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6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in the human placenta for discovery of nuclear
7 factors associated with specification to maintenance of the placental lineage from the fetal tissues. Nuclear
8 receptors expressed in the placenta included Nr6a1, Nr2c2, Nr1d2, Nr5a2, Nr2f2 and Nr3c1. Transcription
9 factors of the Zbtb family expressed in the placenta included Zbtb21, Zbtb44, Zbtb39, Zbtb11 and Zbtb33.
10 Lineage and pioneer transcription factors Gata1 and Gata6 were placental expressed along with general
11 transcription factors with Gtf2h5 and Gtf3c5. The human placenta expressed Twist and Nfatc4 and Myop, a
12 Myb-related factor. The human placenta was Sox14+ and Tcf3+ Tcf21+. We described here a basic
13 transcriptional program that defines the nuclear factor make-up of the placenta in humans.
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